

New measurements in fixed-target collisions at LHCb

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Abstract

The LHCb spectrometer has the unique capability to function as a fixed-target experiment by injecting gas into the LHC beam-pipe while proton or ion beams are circulating. The resulting beam+gas collisions cover a poorly explored energy range that is above previous fixed-target experiments, but below the top RHIC energy for AA collisions. Here we present new results on antiproton and charm production from p He, p Ne, and PbNe fixed-target collisions at LHCb. Comparisons with various theoretical models of particle production and transport through the nucleus will be discussed.

1 The fixed-target program at LHCb

The LHCb fixed-target system, called SMOG (System for Measuring the Overlap with Gas) [1], was originally conceived for precise luminosity calibration of colliding proton beams. The SMOG system allows to inject a low flow rate of noble gas into the vacuum vessel of the LHCb vertex detector (VELO). This has been successfully exploited to obtain very precise luminosity measurements through the beam-gas imaging technique.

Figure 1: Left: dedicated SMOG runs collected since 2015, using different gas types and beam energies. Right: accessible range in the (x, Q^2) plane of the LHCb fixed-target configuration (orange area) compared to other existing experiments.

As an additional important feature, SMOG gives the unique opportunity to operate an LHC experiment in fixed-target mode, and to study proton-nucleus and nucleus-nucleus collisions on various target types and at different center-of-mass energies. Several dedicated runs have already been performed since 2015 using He, Ar, or Ne targets with proton and lead beams at energies ranging from 2.5 TeV to 6.5 TeV, as shown in Fig.1. In particular, fixed-target collisions occurring at an energy in the center of mass of up to 115 GeV, offer an unprecedented opportunity to investigate partons carrying a large fraction of the target nucleon momentum by covering backward and mid rapidities in the centre-of-mass frame. This allows to disclose a new, rich and ambitious physics program at the LHC, exploiting the unique fixed-target kinematics achievable with beam energies at the TeV scale.

2 New measurements

In recent years two analyses based on SMOG data, regarding the prompt antiproton production in p He collisions and charmed mesons production in p He and p Ar collisions, have been published [2,3]. Here we present the results of three new analyses regarding the charm production in p Ne and PbNe collisions and the antiproton production in p He collisions.

Charmonium production in p Ne collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 68.5$ GeV

In this analysis, the production of J/ψ is studied in collisions of protons with energy of 2.5 TeV incident on Ne nuclei at rest, corresponding to a center-of-mass energy of $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 68.5$ GeV [4].

The measured J/ψ cross-section per target nucleon is consistent with previous results at different energies. The J/ψ differential cross-sections per target nucleon is shown as a function of p_T in Fig.2 (left) and is compared with two theoretical models: HELAC-Onia underestimate the J/ψ differential cross-sections, while R. Vogt's predictions with (1%) and without Intrinsic Charm contribution both reproduce quite well the data. Furthermore, the first measurement made in the LHCb fixed-target configuration of the $\psi(2S)$ over J/ψ ratio is also reported. This measurements is in good agreement with other proton-nucleus measurements performed at different centre-of-mass energies by different experiments, as shown in Fig.2 (right).

Figure 2: Left: the J/ψ differential cross-sections per target nucleon, as a function of p_T , compared to theoretical predictions. Right: the $\psi(2S)$ to J/ψ cross-section ratio as a function of the target atomic mass number (A).

J/ψ and D_0 production in PbNe collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 68.5$ GeV

In this study, the first measurement of J/ψ to D_0 production ratio by the LHCb experiment in its fixed-target configuration [5] is reported.

The ratio between the J/ψ and the D_0 production cross-section is studied as a function of rapidity, transverse momentum and centrality. The $\sigma_{J/\psi}/\sigma_{D_0}$ ratio is compatible with no dependence on rapidity, whereas a strong p_T dependence is observed, as can be seen in the left plot of Fig.3. The right plot of Fig.3 shows the measurement of the ratio as a function of the number of binary nucleon-nucleon collisions, N_{coll} , corresponding to different centrality intervals related to the overlap region between the two colliding nuclei. The decreasing trend of the ratio can be explained by the fact that the J/ψ production is affected by additional cold nuclear-matter effects with respect to D_0 . Therefore, within the uncertainties, there is no evidence of an anomalous suppression related to the formation of a deconfined medium.

Figure 3: Ratios of J/ψ to D_0 cross-sections as function of (left) transverse momentum and (right) binary nucleon-nucleon collisions.

Measurement of detached antiproton production in $p\text{He}$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 110$ GeV

This analysis presents the production of \bar{p} from anti-hyperon decays, relatively to the prompt \bar{p} production, from fixed-target $p\text{He}$ collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 110$ GeV [6] and complements the published measurement of prompt antiproton production obtained from the same data sample [2].

At this energy scale, the anti-hyperon contributions to the antiproton production are observed to be significantly larger than predictions of most commonly used hadronic production models. Antiprotons produced in this way can experimentally be distinguished from prompt \bar{p} in LHCb by the exploiting the separation between their origin vertex and the primary $p\text{He}$ collision vertex. The dominant anti-hyperon contribution, namely $\bar{\Lambda} \rightarrow \bar{p}\pi^+$ from promptly produced $\bar{\Lambda}$ particles, is also exclusively measured. This analysis reports the measurements of the ratios:

$$R_{\bar{H}} \equiv \frac{\sigma(p\text{He} \rightarrow \bar{H}X \rightarrow \bar{p}X)}{\sigma(p\text{He} \rightarrow \bar{p}_{\text{prompt}}X)}, \quad R_{\bar{\Lambda}} \equiv \frac{\sigma(p\text{He} \rightarrow \bar{\Lambda}X \rightarrow \bar{p}X)}{\sigma(p\text{He} \rightarrow \bar{p}_{\text{prompt}}X)} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{H} is defined as any strange anti-hyperon. As shown in Fig. 4, the most commonly used hadronic collision generators underestimate the anti-hyperon contribution to the \bar{p} production in both inclusive and exclusive approaches. These results are thus expected to provide a valuable input to improve the predictions for the secondary \bar{p} cosmic flux.

Figure 4: Results of (left) $R_{\bar{H}}$ and (right) $R_{\bar{\Lambda}}$, as a function of the \bar{p} transverse momentum.

3 The upgrade of the fixed-target: SMOG2

The SMOG2 project constitutes an upgrade of the original SMOG system [7]. The new setup consists of a storage cell, installed at the upstream edge of the VELO, coaxial with the LHC beam, and an advanced Gas Feed System (GFS). The main advantage of SMOG2 is the possibility to increase the target gas density by up to two orders of magnitude at the same gas injection flow rate of SMOG. This will boost the target areal density by a factor of 8 to 35 depending on the injected gas species.

One of the key features of SMOG2 is that it allows for a significantly more precise determination of the target density (thus of the luminosity) together with the possibility to inject H_2 and D_2 in addition to all noble gases. In particular, the use of H_2 and D_2 targets, available for the first time at the LHC, would open new physics frontiers that include the study of the proton structure in terms of quark and gluon distributions at unique kinematic conditions. Moreover, thanks to the displaced interaction region (determined by the cell length and position) with respect to the nominal collider interaction point, it could be possible to run in parallel to the collider mode.

4 Conclusions

The LHCb fixed-target program offers rich physics opportunities with excellent detector performance and unique kinematic coverage. Three new analyses regarding the charm production in pNe and $PbNe$ and the antiproton production in pHe have been presented, further demonstrating that the LHCb detector is perfectly suited to reconstruct events from fixed-target collisions. The upgraded SMOG system (SMOG2), based on the use of a storage cell for the target gas, has been already installed and will significantly enhance the performances of fixed-target physics at LHCb, disclosing a broad and ambitious physics program.

References

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